

DIPLOMA

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY JURNALIDA

Yuldasheva A.Z

**Methodologies of business process reengineering model for
e-government**

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

Bosh muharrir:
A.A. Abdurahmonov

2022/NOYABR

★ ★ ★ ★ ★
HONORED
MENTION
★ ★ ★ ★ ★

YOUR
SEAL